

Notes on the rare nursery-web spider *Walrencea globosa* Blandin, 1979 in South Africa (Araneae: Pisauridae)

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ABSTRACT

Notes on the rare nursery-web spider *Walrencea globosa* Blandin, 1979 are provided. The species was previously known only from the type locality in South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed and live photographs are provided, with notes on their lifestyle.

Key words: Afrotropical, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, SANSa

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Walrencea*, described by Blandin (1979), is monotypic and known from only one South African species, *Walrencea globosa* Blandin, 1979. The type locality was only given as Natal. Although illustrated, the description of the species was poor and identification is still problematic. The status of the species therefore remained obscure. However, during surveys as part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida, some more specimens were sampled from a locality in the Eastern Cape.

METHODS

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), surveys were undertaken in different parts of the country. The first author surveyed large areas in the Eastern Cape. During these surveys, spiders were sampled and photographed, and the voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council—Plant Health and Protection division. It was while identifying some problem species that we discovered the *Walrencea globosa* specimens. The species was collected while surveying Thyspunt (34°10.424'S, 24°40.344'E). It is a rocky stretch of coast approximately 12 km WNW of Cape Saint Francis in the Eastern Cape province of South Africa. It is just west of the beach Thysbaai and south-east of Oyster Bay. The site has been identified as a possible location for a nuclear reactor to be built by South African electricity utility Eskom.

TAXONOMY

Walrencea globosa Blandin, 1979

Figures 1-9

Walrencea globosa Blandin, 1979: 369, figs 5, 15, 24, 35, 41.

COMMON NAME: This genus was named by Blandin (1979) after Dr Lawrence, hence the common name, Lawrence's Nursery-web Spiders.

DESCRIPTION: Size TL 8-9 mm. Carapace: a little longer than wide; narrower in eye area (Fig. 1); cephalic region broad; fovea short; carapace covered with pale setae; a white median line bordered by darker setae; number of teeth of the posterior margins of the chelicera variable (2 to 4); eyes eight in two rows (Fig. 2); ocular lines occupy a wide space; anterior row recurved; median ocular triangle longer than wide. Abdomen with slightly

Figures 1-4. *Walrencea globosa*. 1. Female habitus; 2. Eye pattern; 3. Epigyne; 4. Male palp (From Blandin 1979).

abdominal folium (darker in male); marked anteriorly with short pale midline framed by dark setae (Figs 5-9); venter pale. Legs same colour as carapace, bearing strong setae. Cephalothorax covered with light hair, on which emerges a single white median line, underlined by a little hairiness. Abdomen shows slightly darker abdominal foliums (more so in males), marked in front by a short clear middle line framed by two dark markings.

Figure 5. *Walrencea globosa*, microscope photograph of female from Thyspunt (Photo: A. Dippenaar-Schoeman).

Figures 6-7. *Walrencea globosa*, immature female from Thyspunt (Photo: L. Wiese).

Figures 8-9. *Walrencea globosa*, female from Thyspunt (Photo: L. Wiese).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern cape:* Thyspunt, 12km WNW of Cape St Francis, leg. L. Wiese, 2012 (NCA 2021/5669). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Sodwana Bay National Park, Mgoboseleni trail (-27.543028, 32.663528), leg. M. Ramirez, Museo Argentino de Ciencias Naturales (Ramirez & Rodríguez 2021).

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